

Who are we? We are a Horizon Europe project that aims to build an extreme data platform that brings together large scale data storage systems and powerful computing infrastructures by implementing novel automated data management and effective data staging.

Welcome to EXAKI

We are thrilled to announce the launch of **EXAKI**, the EXA4MIND Kickstarter Initiative.

EXAKI provides IT solution architects and data scientists from research organisations, SMEs and industry with all the tools they need to make the most of the [EXA4MIND](#) platform, offering modules of the EXA4MIND software stack that **boost big and extreme data applications**. They will learn how to select and deploy the relevant modules for their use case through training and documentation.

EXAKI provides technical documentation, training, and support for implementing Extreme-Scale Data Solutions in projects. Whether they are developing next-generation analytical applications, integrating extreme-scale data processing into existing systems or exploring how advanced computing can transform their research outcomes, **EXAKI provides the know-how to succeed**. EXAKI's

documentation, guides and code examples simplify implementation and integration and help users' projects succeed.

To make the user experience more intuitive and enable users to make the most of all the resources offered by EXAKI, the initiative uses a **training centre** as its main tool. The [EXAKI training centre](#) provides specialist support to help organisations adopt and implement EXA4MIND technologies across a range of applications. In addition to this training, EXAKI has a repository in which all the [technical documentation](#) related to API references, and code examples for leveraging EXA4MIND modules and the LEXIS Platform 2 is stored.

[Explore EXAKI](#)

EXAKI goals

EXAKI has one main objective: **support and guide** IT solution architects and data scientists from research organisations, SMEs, and industry on their **journey towards optimum use of extreme data**. To do so, EXAKI's technical and multimedia content helps users to get the most out of the EXA4MIND platform.

EXA4MIND addresses a key challenge from the exponential growth of scientific and industrial ability to exploit them. It achieves this by connecting powerful computing infrastructures with sophisticated data management systems. Through **EXAKI**, we are **making these capabilities accessible across disciplines**. The EXA4MIND project has already [demonstrated the potential of its platform](#) in fields such as molecular dynamics simulations, automotive camera data analysis, smart agriculture, and health data mining.

Already available training sessions

Explore the knowledge resources that are already available.

POP-3D: Open-Vocabulary 3D Occupancy Prediction from Images

TRAINING
PROVIDED BY
EXA4MIND

POP-3D: OPEN-VOCABULARY 3D OCCUPANCY PREDICTION FROM IMAGES

ANTONÍN VOBECKÝ

CZECH TECHNICAL
UNIVERSITY & VALEO

Funded by
the European Union

In this session, we present a joint work produced in collaboration between [CIIRC CTU](#) from Prague and [Valeo.ai](#) within the EXA4MIND project.

This work focuses on leveraging multimodal learning, particularly language-vision integration, to enable open-vocabulary 3D scene understanding. This is based on our work called "POP-3D: Open-Vocabulary 3D Occupancy Prediction from Images", which was presented at NeurIPS.

Watch the complete video
session

Inference Training with Retrieval Augmented Generation

TRAINING
PROVIDED BY
EXA4MIND

INFERENCE TRAINING WITH RETRIEVAL AUGMENTED GENERATION

FIRAT CENIKEL & GORKEM OZER

MIDDLE EAST TECHNICAL
UNIVERSITY (METU)

Funded by
the European Union

This webinar, hosted by the [Middle East Technical University](#), introduces the EXA4MIND AI Inference Service, which supports advanced querying capabilities in high-performance computing (HPC) environments. During the training

session, a local implementation of Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) is showcased, demonstrating how it can enhance the precision of large language model (LLM) responses.

The session walks through a complete RAG pipeline —from preprocessing a university knowledge base into manageable chunks, generating vector embeddings using an embedding model, to storing these embeddings in a vector database for semantic similarity search. The training concludes by demonstrating how to send an API request to the inference service using the enriched prompt.

Watch the complete video session

Use of Vector Data Bases in AI Pipelines

This webinar, organised by the [Middle East Technical University](#), focuses on the fundamentals and practical use of vector databases for similarity search tasks in AI workflows.

The session begins with an introduction to core concepts such as vector embeddings and how they enable semantic understanding of data. Different types of vector search—including image vector search, text vector search, and hybrid approaches—are discussed conceptually to provide foundational understanding. In the hands-on part of the webinar, Milvus is used to create a vector database collection and load both image and text embeddings. Participants are guided through code demonstrations showing how to perform various search operations and analyse the results in real-time.

Watch the complete video

ETL Integration with EXA4MIND for Optimized Data Workflows

In this session, we introduce the [ALTRNATIV](#) ETL Tool integration with EXA4MIND platform, its end-to-end integration with the EXA4MIND Extreme Data Databases (EDD).

You will first see how ALTRNATIV's ETL intuitive web interface and processing boxes enable rapid data loading, transformation, and pipeline orchestration directly against EXA4MIND EDD. We then walk through a complete workflow securing health-care data pipelines, enforcing GDPR-compliant handling, and monitoring for reliability, so you understand both the technical and governance aspects.

Finally, we'll demonstrate a real-world SME health application, showcasing data enrichment, population level demographic analysis, and interactive disease tracking workflows built using ALTRNATIV ETL Tool and EXA4MIND platform.

[Watch the complete video session](#)

Upcoming training sessions

Keep an eye out for these upcoming events:

- **Use of DASK to speed up cache updation.**

- Author: TERRAVIEW.
 - Date: **September 2025**.
 - Type: Webinar.
- **Leverage optimum data-management backends for Big and Extreme Data Analytics with EXA4MIND.**
 - Author: Leibniz Supercomputing Centre.
 - Date: **September 2025**.
 - Type: Hands-on session.
- **Leveraging EXA4MIND with ETL Solutions for Extreme Data Analytics.**
 - Author: ALTRNATIV.
 - Date: **September 2025**.
 - Type: Industry engagement.
- **Apache Airflow in the context of Supercomputing and data processing.**
 - Author: IT4Innovations.
 - Date: **September 2025**.
 - Type: Webinar.
- **Data transfer between DBMS, object storage & supercomputing systems data.**
 - Author: IT4Innovations.
 - Date: **September 2025**.
 - Type: Webinar.
- **Valeo application case in EXA4MIND.**
 - Author: Valeo.
 - Date: **September 2025**, at the Czech European Researchers' Night.
 - Type: Hands-on session.
- **Supercomputing with Optimum Data Backends — EXA4MIND.**
 - Author: Leibniz Supercomputing Centre.
 - Date: **October 2025**.
 - Type: Hands-on session / summer school.
- **How Airflow powers Aquaview.**
 - Author: TERRAVIEW.
 - Date: **October 2025**.
 - Type: Webinar.
- **Aquaview service capabilities — how to optimize water use in fields.**
 - Author: TERRAVIEW.
 - Date: **October 2025**.
 - Type: Industry engagement.
- **Valeo Technical Evening: BIG DATA APPLICATION ON HPC.**
 - Author: Valeo.
 - Date: **November 2025**.
 - Type: Industry engagement.
- **DATA NEXUS Cluster: joint session.**
 - Author: AUSTRALO.
 - Date: **November 2025**.

- Type: Webinar.
 - **FAIR Research Data Management in data-driven workflows with EXA4MIND.**
 - Author: Leibniz Supercomputing Centre.
 - Date: **January 2026.**
 - Type: Hands-on session.
 - **IDA & ADAMS4SIMS: Accelerating Force Field Development through Smart MD Data Integration.**
 - Author: IT4Innovations.
 - Date: **February 2026.**
 - Type: Hands-on session.
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